

TALENT RETENTION STRATEGIES - INTERVENTIONS OF CROSS CULTURAL MANAGEMENT

BUILD A CULTURE; EMPLOYEES WANT TO BE A PART OF

¹Dr. RAJINI.G and ²SIVASAKTHI KUMAR

¹ Director -Institutional Collaborations and MoU, Professor & Head- MBA (General), School of Management Studies, Vels Institute of Science and Technology & Advanced Studies, Chennai, India.

Email Id - dr.rajini.g@gmail.com

² Corresponding author * - Research Scholar, School of Management Studies, Vels Institute of Science and Technology & Advanced Studies, Chennai. Email Id – reachmesivasakthi@gmail.com

Abstract

The economies globally are developing post the pandemic talent management strategies still not have got proper recognition globally. The transformation of global talent management is affected by its culture and other difference. Exploring the influencers of talent retention strategies in global multinational corporations will be add on for companies to understand the key factors that should be taken into consideration. A quantitative look over was adopted and data was collected among 223 respondents globally among multinational companies. A self-administered autonomous structured questionnaire was used for data collection, statistical package SPSS 22 was used for analysing the quantified data. The study result found that the key determinants of retention strategies are performance and recognition, career development, covid-19 initiatives, global communications and the demographics do not have direct difference with the retention strategies. The study recommends that companies to make people in the organization more cross culturally aware and must pay ears to the employees on the aspects discussed in detailed to enable them stay long in the organization.

Keywords: Separation Rate, Talent Management, Internal Mobility, Retention Strategies, Cross Cultural Management

INTRODUCTION:

In today's diversity at workplace, the complexity raised while formulation retention strategies for employees who work globally. As leaders it is important to identify and analyse the shortfalls and develop skills and give the existing employees insights so that they retain better in the organization. Developing a highly engaging workplace and bringing in a contended environment calls for a strong retention strategies in place Management (2022). The hybrid work culture have becomes hot topic post lockdown, thus integrating employees of cross culture calls for a strong rewarding effort, hiring right fit, employees well-being, CSR programs, ESOP, altering work responsibilities, reduced workdays, open global communication, shaping growth and development and listening to employees feedback says Management (2022). Employee job satisfaction and engagement are the vital ingredients for companies to face a lesser separation rate by increasing their retention rate. A critical issue that companies are facing today is the secret behind how to retain employees who possess extraordinary competencies and be ahead of the competition in the market. It is the duty of companies to anticipate these shortages and pitfalls. There is a higher chance of weathering the pitfalls by systematically managing the retention strategies in both good and bad times. The

Talent acquisition professionals in the global force survey reveal that employee recognition and engagement efforts will have a good inclination towards retaining employees. The reason for retaining could be turnover is expensive, it might affect the performance of the organization, and turnover will result in a negative image of the company. While not all turnover is considered to be harmful but turnover often results in a negative performance of the company. At times turnover is considered to be beneficial when a new hire proves to be more productive than the previous worker. The drivers of employee retention need to be understood in order to reduce the separation rate. In order for an organization to have a better engaging workforce, the employer must be responsive to the voice of the employees. Prior to the Covid-19 pandemic, the situation was different and now it is different. SHRM's (2018) Flexible work survey revealed that employees want to be recognized for the work they do and see it as an achievement. This study by Roy Maurer (2019) agreed that recognizing employees will have a positive impact on their work culture and the overall employee experience. A study of Internal Mobility by Roy Maurer (2020) stays those employees who find an opportunity to pass through their organization either vertically or horizontally are more likely to stay in an organization. It is a true fact that when employees feel they have no control over their success they will become disengaged. Thus in order to bring in a sense of belonging and control among the people at work, employees must communicate their feedback, expectations, and routine. Thus it is the duty of the HR managers working in Multinational Corporation to ensure the people working in their organization are happy and will continue to work with an improved spirit. And be a boost to the company and its success. It is the duty to listen to the employees in order to decide how they feel in terms of their alignment with the goals of the organization and how are they opinioned on the performance and recognition and the career development opportunities that they receive from the company where they are a part of and how they feel valued in a team, the working environment safety measures which the company takes in order to protect their employees so that they feel they are valued, it is the duty of the companies to understand the what the employees felt about the retention strategies, and how are they able to communicate globally, it is the obligation of the employer to understand the customer service and flexible working from the home option of how people at work feel so changes can be made to favour the employees and keep them happy and stay connected with the company for having a delighted experience.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

In recent times talent retention is seen as personnel literature. Companies, industries, firms, and small and big organizations have a widespread usage of talent management strategies when it comes to attracting, selecting, developing, and deploying with not just that also involving them engaging them and retaining the best-talented employees. Talent management is a careful and deliberate perspective undertaken in order to attract high potential candidates, develop them and retain people who possess the extreme amount of aptitude in order to meet the requirements Davis, Cutt, Flynn, and Mowl (2016). (Arif and Uddin, 2016) Global talent management comprises all organizational key activities that to attract the right talent from the candidate pool, select them, engage the new joiners, develop the employees and retain the best talent who

are in the most strategic or key roles on a global scale. Dalkir (2013) Talent is not just about having a good amount of knowledge, or skill, it is not even about just having both mental and physical ability to do something, it is now the brainpower alone it is but to do something out of the box and be different. Dive and Theme (2015) Sharing knowledge by having social forums or organizations both formally and informally will help each other in the organization by improving the connection with each other and developing an affiliation thus helps in retention Arif and Uddin, 2016; Ghotnian et al. (2019) employees performances are the metrics of their effectiveness, and efficiency and sees if the pay is appropriate to the job that they do. Prarthana Ghosh (2021) says for continuous improvement of the companies there needs to be continuous improvement of employees. Employees must be given the scope and opportunity to grow and advance in their careers. Rewards and recognition become an integral part of an employee's tenure in an organization by giving rewards and recognition employees feel they are cared for by the organization. Rewards and recognition are most needed in order to motivate, manage and engage good employees. A major reason why employees stay in an organization or stay with their team is that they find might be well trained or developed in their career due to that company. Heathfield (2008) says employee retention depends mainly on developing employees and thus an on-the-job training model will have great employee growth. SHRM (2014) enumerates clearly the objective that the vision, mission, values, policies, and purpose of the organization will help employees align their individual goals and thus create a coherent environment. Suryanarayana (2010) in the present competing environment organizations can give winning results by strategic intent, by doing so this will ensure if employees are dedicated to the organization's vision mission, and goal and able to match their own.

METHODOLOGY:

This work was based on both primary and secondary data. The data was collected among 223 respondents by using a well-structured questionnaire that consisted of 43 questions under the 9 variables organizational goal, performance and recognition, career development strategies, teamwork, customer services, covid-19 initiatives, work from initiatives, global communication, and retention strategies. Since it is believed that retention happens in and through 2 or 3 levels in big-sized companies (Bernthal&Wellins, 2006) the study was conducted among middle management and senior management, the ones who are responsible for a team (Rothwell&Kazanas, 1999) of the companies located globally like Australia, New Zealand, China, Germany, Hong Kong, India, Indonesia, Portugal, Australia, Belgium, France, Ireland, Italy, Netherlands, Spain, Michigan, Missouri, North Carolina, South Carolina, Tennessee, Georgia, Banbury, Bicester, Bristol, Chorley, Milnsbridgea. The data so gathered was analyzed using SPSS 22 using ANOVA, Correlation, and Regression.

DATA ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION:

Table 1: Reliability Analysis

Variables	Cronbach Alpha Value	Items
Organizational Goals	0.738	3
Performance And Recognition	0.896	6
Career Development	0.893	7
Teamwork	0.844	3
Customer Services	0.884	4
Covid 19 Initiative	0.930	6
Work From Home Initiative	0.848	5
Communication	0.898	6
Retention Strategies	0.750	3
Total	0.939	43

Table 1 interprets the scale reliability test. The Cronbach value for all items used in the study shows .939 which is greater than the threshold value of 0.7 and it implies that the scale is adequate to test each construct. Each construct values are 0.738, 0.896, 0.893, 0.844, 0.844, 0.930, 0.848, 0.898, .750 for the construct organizational goals, performance and recognition, career development, teamwork, customer services, covid19 initiatives, work from the home initiative, global communication and retention strategies shows the value greater than 0.6 which indicates those dimensions are adequate for the study.

One Way Analysis of Variance

Table 2: ANOVA between Designation Grades on Retention Strategies

Study Variables			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
Retention Strategies	Between Groups	(Combined)	13.631	3	4.544	2.15	0.095	
		Linear Term	Un-weighted	11.421	1	11.421	5.404	0.021
			Weighted	3.061	1	3.061	1.448	0.23
			Deviation	10.57	2	5.285	2.501	0.084
	Within Groups		475.531	225	2.113			
	Total		489.162	228				

H1: There is a significant difference between Designation Grades on Retention Strategies.

The table 2 interpret that the p-value 0.095 which is greater than 0.05 significant values. It results that there is no significant difference in the mean value of the designation grades retention strategies. This means that irrespective of the grade to which an employee belongs to the retention strategies will not have an effect.

Table 3: ANOVA between Age Group Based on Retention Strategies

Study Variables			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
Retention Strategies	Between Groups	(Combined)	14.25	7	2.036	0.947	0.471	
		Linear Term	Unweighted	0.91	1	0.91	0.423	0.516
			Weighted	7.088	1	7.088	3.298	0.071
			Deviation	7.162	6	1.194	0.555	0.765
	Within Groups		474.912	221	2.149			
	Total		489.162	228				

H2: There is a significant difference between Age Group on Retention Strategies.

The table 3 interpret that the p-value 0.471 which is greater than 0.05 significant values. It results that there is no significant difference in the mean value of the age and retention strategies. This means that the employee age does not determine the retention strategies directly or indirectly.

Table 4: ANOVA between Departments Based on Retention Strategies

Study Variables			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
Retention Strategies	Between Groups	(Combined)	14.25	7	2.036	0.947	0.471	
		Linear Term	Un-weighted	0.91	1	0.91	0.423	0.516
			Weighted	7.088	1	7.088	3.298	0.071
			Deviation	7.162	6	1.194	0.555	0.765
	Within Groups		474.912	221	2.149			
	Total		489.162	228				

H3: There is a significant difference between Departments on Retention Strategies.

The table 4 interpret that the p-value 0.471 which is greater than 0.05 significant values. It results that there is no significant difference in the mean value of the department and retention strategies. This means that the retention strategies have no role to play with the department in which an employee works for.

Table 5: ANOVA between Work Experiences Based on Study Variables

Study Variables			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
Retention Strategies	Between Groups	(Combined)	18.489	4	4.622	2.2	0.07	
		Linear Term	Un-weighted	0.134	1	0.134	0.064	0.801
			Weighted	0.944	1	0.944	0.449	0.503
			Deviation	17.545	3	5.848	2.783	0.042
	Within Groups		470.673	224	2.101			
Total		489.162	228					

H4: There is a significant difference between work experiences on Retention Strategies.

The table 5 interpret that the p-value 0.07 which is greater than 0.05 significant values. It results that there is no significant difference in the mean value of the work experiences and retention strategies. This means the irrespective f the years of experience of an employee it has no effect on the employee retention strategies.

Table 6: ANOVA between Gender-Based on Study Variables

Study Variables			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
Retention Strategies	Between Groups	(Combined)	5.027	1	5.027	2.357	0.126	
		Linear Term	Un-weighted	5.027	1	5.027	2.357	0.126
			Weighted	5.027	1	5.027	2.357	0.126
	Within Groups		484.134	227	2.133			
	Total		489.162	228				

H5: There is a significant difference between Genders on Retention Strategies.

The table 6 interpret that the p-value 0.126 which is greater than 0.05 significant values. It results that there is no significant difference in the mean value of the gender retention and strategies. This means whether male or female has no significant difference on retention strategies.

Table 7: Consolidated Tables for One-way ANOVA

Description	Retention Strategies
Designation	NS
Age	NS
Department	NS
Work Experience	NS
Gender	NS

The above table 7 indicates a consolidated understanding of the one way ANOVA that was conducted. It is inferred that the demographic variables like grade, age, department, work experience; gender does not have significant difference on the retention strategies.

REGRESSION ANALYSIS

The main aim of this concept is to find the linear combinations of independent variables and correlate them with the dependent variable.

Multiple regression in order to identify the effects in the combination of the independent variables that is (organizational goal X1, performance and recognition X2, career development X3, Team work X4, customer service X5, covid19 initiatives X6, work from home initiatives X7, global communications X8) against the dependent variable (retention strategies)

$$Y1a = C1a + b1aX1 + b2aX2 + b3aX3 + b4aX4 + b5aX5 + b6aX6 + b7aX7 + b8aX8$$

H2: Retention Strategies can be influenced by organizational goals, performance, and recognition, teamwork, customer services, covid19 initiatives, and work from initiatives, global communication, and career development strategies.

Table 8: Model Summaries

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
.814 ^a	0.663	0.649	0.83575
Predictors (Constant): organizational goal, performance and recognition, team work, customer services, covid 19 initiatives, work from initiatives, global communication and career development strategies			
Dependent: Retention Strategies			

Table 9 model summary inferences that the ability of predictors of Retention Strategies articulated by the R-value 0.814 and R2 value 0.663 which results that 66.3% of variance exists in the dependent variable from the independent variables. It shows that the model is effective enough to determine the relationship. The adjusted R2 value of 0.649 which does not show much deviation from the R2 value indicates that the model is good enough to determine the dependent variable Retention Strategies of the employees.

Table 9: ANOVA

Model 2	Sum Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	269.323	8	33.665	48.198	.001^b
Residual	136.901	196	0.698		
Total	406.224	204			

P value in table 4 is .001 which is less than 0.05 and shows significantly the model is fit. The F value of 48.198 shows there is an existence of a relationship between the retention strategies and its independent variables.

Table 10: Coefficients

Model 2	Un standardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	0.713	0.591		1.206	0.229
Organisation Goal	0.067	0.064	0.070	1.045	0.297
Performance and Recognition	0.072	0.034	0.167	2.125	0.035
Career Development	0.128	0.030	0.339	4.280	0.000
Teamwork	0.036	0.064	0.041	0.554	0.580
Customer Services	-0.053	0.050	-0.065	-1.064	0.289
Covid 19 Initiatives	0.118	0.038	0.220	3.137	0.002
Work From Home Initiatives	0.005	0.032	0.010	0.158	0.874
Global Communication	0.088	0.039	0.160	2.274	0.024

a. Dependent Variable: Retention Strategies

The above table 11 illustrates that the beta value for organizational goal is 0.067, teamwork is 0.036, customer services are -0.053, and work from initiatives 0.005. There is no significant relationship between organizational goal, teamwork, customer services, and work-from-home initiatives ($p = 0.297, 0.580, 0.289,$ and 0.874) at a 5% confidence interval that shows a greater value than 0.05. There is a significant relationship between performance and recognition, career development, covid19 initiatives and global communication with respect to Retention Strategies as their p values are 0.035, 0.000, 0.002, and 0.024 which is significant with the confidence interval of 5%, and their corresponding beta values for performance and recognition is 0.072, career development is 0.128, covid 19 initiatives 0.118 and global communication is 0.088. Thereby the final regression equation is derived by incorporating the coefficients as follows:

Retention Strategies = 0.067 (organizational goal) + 0.072 (Performance and recognition) + 0.128 (career development) + 0.036 (teamwork) - 0.053 (customer services) + 0.118 (covid 19 initiatives) + 0.005 (work from home initiatives) + 0.088 (global communication).

Chart 1: Regression Standardized Residual

A Residual is basically the distance from the data point and prediction line. This histogram proves that the data is normally distributed.

Chart 2: Observed Cum Prob

DISCUSSIONS:

In businesses today it is highly important for global leaders to build a talent pool within the organization in order to promote the company and grow at par with the competition. It is important for organizations to keep revising their strategies to win the cutthroat competition. It is highly crucial for global leaders of big multinational corporations to integrate the people working in the organization for a smooth functioning of the businesses. The best weapon to survive in a competitive scenario and bet against the competition is by having good talent management practices (Bratton &Waton, 2018). In order to have a good talent pipeline is a must to have Retention Strategies in place (Muhammad & Shao, 2013) integrating the organizational goal, performance, and recognition, teamwork, customer services, covid19 initiatives, work from initiatives, global communication, and career development strategies of employees. By keeping this in mind the overall objective of the study was to see the influencing factors of retention strategies in an organization so that the separation rate is less. The demographics of the employees working in the global multinational corporation do not have any significance towards the retention strategies of the employees. Similarly, the demographic factor 'age' doesn't have any connection with the variables. The population tally 'designation' proves to have a significant difference with customer service. From the above plot, we are able to identify that 'department' has a significant difference with all other variables other than Covid19 initiatives which clearly proves that departments within the organization are concerned about the safety measures offices are taking for this purpose. The work experience of the employees determines the significant difference between performance & recognition meaning experienced employees perform better and is given good recognition and Covid19 initiatives, while other variable does not have a significant difference.

The goals of the organization and performance & recognition have significant differences with the gender of the employees. Thus employees show more spirit and are inclined towards the goals of the company while for other variables there is no significant difference. The above study shows that there is a high correlation among variables. The variables are also directly proportional to each other. The confidence levels of the variables are 99%. From the regression analysis, it is a well-proven fact that Retention Strategies are influenced by an organizational goal, performance, and recognition, teamwork, customer services, covid19 initiatives, and work from initiatives, global communication, and career development strategies. The study concludes by saying that in order to have a better retention rate the company must focus on performance and recognition of employees, career development, better communication (globally), and most importantly covid 19 initiatives, it is of true concern that the pandemic has taken a turn on people's lives, thus employees are pretty cautious and concerned about the sanitization safety and health. It is suggested that multinational corporate consider and pay more attention to employee performance & recognition, their career development, improve better global communication, and take good and safe covid19 initiatives will bring in a sense of belongingness to the employees, where they feel they are a part of the company, and feel valued thus extending their stay in the organization and working happily for the company. This study is of good use to the HR managers working in Multinational Corporations and other private and public companies in order to understand the most influencing factors of Retention

Strategies. Further, this study will be of good use to the academicians, and students working in this research area.

CONCLUSION:

The study symbolizes an equitable attempt to scrutinize the relationship among retention strategies and organizational goals, performance, and recognition, teamwork, customer services, covid19 initiatives, work from initiatives, global communication, and career development strategies of employees. Organizations today are spending huge amounts on bringing in the best talents and hiring them. Thus it becomes the duty of the talent acquisition professionals to manage the talented workforce, keep them in good spirit and get the best out of them and definitely make efforts to retain them. This study has few limitations like this was conducted only among the corporate companies situated globally, while the results will vary with conducting this kind of a study in a particular region or geographical area. Another curb would be it was conducted among corporate companies and thus will generate different results when conducted in other streams like automobiles, education, R and D, and so on. Interventions in cross cultural management calls ways to integrate people in the organization and make them stay longer. Talent management always calls for a strategic approach in order to anticipate the pitfalls and be prepared without any stop. Thus having a map in hand will definitely improve the retention rate in the organization and thus enable in achievement big goals in collaboration with a talented workforce. The retention strategies not only just focus on retention but also ensure upgrading the skills and upscale the employees thus creating a win-win. Thus it is the duty of the HR leaders to enlighten organizations more cross culturally aware.

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The Authors report there is no competing interest to declare

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APPENDICES:

List of Tables

Table Number	Table Heading	Page Number
1	Reliability Analysis	4
2	ANOVA between Designation Grades with Retention Strategies	5
3	ANOVA between Age Group Based on Retention Strategies	5
4	ANOVA between Departments Based on Retention Strategies	6
5	ANOVA between Work Experiences Based on Retention Strategies	6
6	ANOVA between Gender-Based on Retention Strategies	7
7	Consolidated Table For One-way ANOVA	7
8	Model Summaries	8
9	ANOVA	9
10	Coefficients	9

List of Charts

Chart Number	Chart Title	Page Number
1	Regression Standardized Residual	10
2	Observed Cum Prob	11

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